

EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGY SUPPORTED INSTRUCTION IN ENHANCING READING SKILLS

Poonam Kumari

Research Scholar, RIE, Utkal University, BBSR

Prof. S.P. Mishra

Former Professor in Education, RIE, BBSR

Abstract

Reading comprehension and reading skills have always been prerequisites for success in many sectors of the educational system as well as in the majority of routine life activities. In the educational field, the increased accessibility of technology and online resources may be a truly valid support, and they also play a key role in enhancing reading abilities. Technology can be a highly effective motivator, for a reader who is having trouble. He or she might like reading from digital texts and doing so while using various mediums. As a result, the NEP 2020 the policy by the Ministry of Education has consented to having students participate in online learning, also known as e-learning, using computers or technology. The usage of social media, cell phones, laptops, and the Internet is ingrained in today's students' daily lives. This is true for students of all ages, from pre-schoolers to adults and those in higher education. Responding to the current global predicament has relied heavily on our ability to employ technology. Technology plays an important role in improving different language skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing. So, in this regard this study aims to investigate how technology-supported instruction affects the students' reading abilities. In order to attain this goal, an achievement test was held to gather data from the students. This study is experimental in nature, using a single group pre-test - post-test approach. The results of this study showed that the use of technology-supported instruction helped students' motivation to read as well as to improve their reading skills and comprehension.

Key Words- Reading Skills, Technology supported instruction, Achievement test, pre-test - post-test approach

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Introduction

Today's technology has developed new ways of making everyone's life easier and more convenient. Technology has changed the lifestyles of human beings. In present time the people becoming more reliant on different technologies to achieve various kind of task. Technologies like- smartphones, smart watches, the internet, computer, WhatsApp, and television all these appear to make lives easier. These emerging technologies are affecting the education field also, technology reshapes the classroom teaching and develops students' skills to perform in the classroom. These skills mainly include Listening, Speaking, Writing and Reading. Among which reading is the fundamental in almost all endeavours of life. It is important because if a child can read, he/she can easily learn anything about everything and everything about anything. Reading is one of the most important skills to aid the successful development of a language. It influences how to interact with the others.

For making a good reader it is the teachers' responsibility to provide the best possible conditions for learning. They have to make their classroom innovative, creative and interesting which encouraged them to learn, love and enjoy reading. Using technology in the classroom is the best way to motivate children to learn, sustain interest, and enhance reading skills. It also helps them in improving vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension.

Technology Supported Instruction is the way of teaching and learning in which content is delivered with the help of technology and this technology includes the internet, audio and video, WhatsApp, Google meet, e-material etc. There is a great impact of these technologies in teaching and learning of language skills. So, it is important to examine the transition from printed text to technology-text affects the way of language students with respect to reading. For this reason, this study examines the effect of technology supported instruction in enhancing reading skills at elementary school students.

Objective

The present paper aims to compare the mean score of pre-test and post-test Hindi reading skill achievement of class 8th students.

Design of the Study

In this study a pre-test was conducted to measure the initial level of the reading skills before treatment and again the same test as a post-test was administered by giving treatment in the form of intervention by teaching with technology supported instructional material. Later on, results of both the test pre-test as well as post-test are compared to find out the differences.

Tool Used

Achievement test was used to investigate the present study. The data was collected from class 8th students. Achievement Test was constructed and developed by the investigator with the help of the supervisor and experts to measure the level of students in reading skill. Students were tested by using a test which is based on the passages that they were taught.

Results and Discussions

The aim of this study is to know the effect of technology supported instruction in enhancing reading skills of the class 8th students with respect to the achievement of the students, the data are as follows:

Group	N	Mean	SD	r	t-value
Pre-Test	110	8.87	2.94	0.54	8.62**
Post-Test	110	11.30	2.54		

** Significant at 0.05 level of Significance

As shown in Table, there was a significant difference in scores of pre-test ($M=8.87$, $SD= 2.94$) and post-test ($M=11.30$, $SD=2.54$). The mean scores of students in the post-test were higher in compare to the pre-test. Therefore, investigator concluded that the use of Technology Supported Instruction such as PowerPoint presentation, SlideShare, Pdf., Video, Audio in teaching reading skills in elementary schools is quite effective. The result of this study shows that the Technology Supported Instruction does play an important role in students' learning and performance. It is found by the investigator that the Technology Supported Instruction makes the learning interesting and students' felt that the content matter was more impressive when it is delivered with the help of technology which further draws the attention of students' and leads to their active participation in the teaching learning process. So, in this way they learn the things with fun and pleasure. Therefore, post-test phase showed better result.

From the findings of this research, it is apparent that reading skill is better developed through Technology Supported Instruction in Hindi Learning students at elementary stage which does affect the achievement through increasing test scores, motivation or facilitation collaborative and interactive learning. This study implies potential benefits from using information technology to improve students' reading skills. The study revealed that technology supported instruction provided a very motivating environment for students by developing reading skills thus, making teaching and learning more pleasurable, relevant and interesting.

Conclusion

Languages are not fixed; they are constantly changing. Technologies like the internet, smartphone, computer, television, etc. are widely used in the development of language skills.

Hence the result of this study indicates that the utilization of Technology Supported Instruction material (ppt. pdf., animation video, audio, image etc.) could help to develop Hindi Reading Skill, as they enhance comprehension, which encourages to process the meaning of the text more deeply and more actively, make reading more interesting and engaging, motivate the students and fosters students' autonomy.

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